

**BETWEEN TWO WORLDS: CULTURAL CONFLICT AND HYBRID IDENTITY
IN PEARL BUCK'S "RELATIVES"**

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Key words: immigrant, transitional, manifest, confrontation, reconciliation, alienation, isolation, provincial, endows, comprehend.

Abstract. In the novel "Relatives," the writer comprehends the cultural processes taking place in the world associated with the conflict of beliefs and values of different generations. The author shows the difficulties that first-generation Chinese immigrants face in their desire to pass on national culture to their heirs, as well as the problems of mixing Western and Eastern cultures, and the clash of "old and new" in the Chinese and American contexts. Buck endows his novel's characters with a transitional, dual, hybrid identity, and places them "somewhere between" the cultures of China and America, presenting to the reader the essence of the dialectic of binary oppositions "belonging - not belonging."

Noticing Dr. Liang among the guests, the theater director invites him to give a speech after the performance: "He was warmed by their pride in him and he took the opportunity to remark that it was the duty of every Chinese to represent his country in the most favorable light to Americans who were, after all, only foreigners." Dr. Liang is proud of the antiquity and richness of his own culture, which he bases solely on Confucian principles. For him, Chinese national identity is most fully manifested in the philosophy of Confucius. Having adapted to American reality, Liang sees himself "noble husband" and a "perfect man": "I hope I am a truly superior man in the conflicted sense, whether I am in China or America."

Dr. Liang personifies the collective image of the Chinese intellectual of the Western type, with whose prototypes Buck has been in constant confrontation since the publication of the novel "Earth." Liang rejects the significance of the Chinese peasantry in the history of the country's development. In a conversation with the Americans, he tries to prove that the Chinese elite is the only engine of Chinese culture: "But I thought most of the people of China were peasants, the guest would reply," "It is quality that is meaningful in any nation, the articulate few, the scholars. Surely men like myself represent more perfectly than peasants the spirit of Chinese civilization. Our nation has always been ruled by our intellectuals. Our emperors depend upon wise men."

The surname "Liang" literally translates from Chinese as "bridge, connection," but the hero's ability to "build bridges between cultures" is assessed very controversially. The narrator calls Liang "ambassador": "in his small way, of course, an ambassador." However, the reader understands that instead of intercultural reconciliation and unification, Liang creates situations of misunderstanding and disorientation.

Discussion. First, as P. Conn metaphorically noted, Dr. Liang portrays China as an "elegant counterfeit", trying to present his country in the most favorable light for Americans: "We should set the example, my child. I often ask Heaven why it is that I am sent here, an exile from my beloved

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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country. Heaven does not answer but my heart makes a reply. I have a mission here. My children have a mission, too. We must show this vast new country what it is to be Chinese.”

Secondly, by living in the Chinese past, Dr. Liang tries to combat his isolation. His character combines such traits as snobbery, arrogance, and a sense of personal superiority. In New York, all people are equally “strangers” to him: he tries to distance himself from both “strangers,” unenlightened Americans, and from the residents of Chinatowns. The feeling of isolation and alienation is especially relevant for Liang in situations of communication with representatives of the Chinese diaspora. The mixture of people with completely different backgrounds - provincial Chinese, merchants, Americanized teenagers - gives Liang a feeling of “displacement”.

His fictional world of idealized Confucianism helps him find balance in his perception of the urbanized Western world. His monologues are permeated with poeticization of the Chinese empire; Dr. Liang sees his mission as preserving the Chinese national cultural heritage in an intact form. In his idealized China, unchanging calm absorbs the disorder and confusion of existence.

Dr. Liang's children belong to both worlds, China and America, to varying degrees, and at the same time do not always fit into them. Living in New York, their ideas about China were largely shaped by their father. They have a romanticized idea of China as their distant homeland, “home,” the place of their national and cultural affiliation: “All of them were sick to get to China”; “Our people are good – our people are wonderful. China is great,” says James, Dr. Liang’s eldest son, to his American lover.

Dr. Liang's children have different views on their connection to China. The eldest son, James, is aware of his inferior status in America. Together with their sister Mary, they long to move to China to experience the greatness of their homeland and be useful to the Chinese people: “China is not weak. She is only in distress. All the great strength is simply waiting until we come to her help. She has lived in an old, old world and she needs to be born into the new one.”

Dr. Liang's youngest children, Peter and Louise - “more American than any American” - were completely Americanized and fully entered into the complex multicultural reality of the United States. This is how he describes Louise: “She comes and goes as if she were not Chinese. She has no breeding. She is not respectful. Now she insults even our ancestors.” Louise is characterized by a deliberate rejection of the cultural and linguistic heritage of China; she is close to American values and the Western type of social behavior.

Arriving in China gave rise to a feeling of “outside home” in Liang. Confronted with modern Chinese reality, they were acutely aware of the gap between their imagined and real China. “One knew the blood was the same, but to have grown up in America and China made two different beings.” Traditional ties with their historical and national past are broken for them.

Having achieved unity with Chinese peasant culture, James concludes: “There was no magic homeland. [only] poverty and oppression, and indifference to both.” He marries a peasant girl, who becomes his assistant in learning about China. In their relationship, Buck sees an alliance between West and East, modernity and tradition. Through his wife, James finds a path to embracing his own hybrid identity.

For Mary, life in the village is connected with the search for “herself,” her roots, and her national identity: “I want to know what kind of people we are. Behind Pa and Ma who are we? Mary finds happiness in a simple life. Having opened a school for village children and married a local Chinese, she sees her mission in reviving the village: “Both Chen and Mary had found a way to root

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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themselves here. James watched Mary and he could discover in her lively looks not one hint of discontent." It is characterized by complete assimilation.

The contrast between the fates of the sisters, Mary and Louise, is interesting. Soon after Louise arrives in China, she meets an American military man, with whom she goes back to New York. Having married an American, Louise becomes a traditional Chinese wife, obedient, meek, and submissive to her husband in everything. Mary, on the other hand, settles in a small Chinese village and takes on the role of a leader fighting for women's rights.

Peter, the youngest son of Dr. Liang, is characterized by a rejection of Chinese reality: "I have been trying to find out. The dirt - the disease - the stupidity... I shall never forgive Pa as long as I live - let us believe that everything was wonderful, hiding it all under a Confucian mist! No wonder he doesn't come back!" Peter accuses the Chinese people of powerlessness, backwardness, and unwillingness to change: "Our country is foul, so he began to write in English. "We must make it clean. Our country is rotten. We must ruthlessly cut away what is rotten and burn it up. A prairie wind, a prairie fire, that is what I see. After the fire the ashes, the clean ashes. Who will light this fire? It can be lit by a single match held in a human hand". Upon learning of Peter's death, Dr. Liang realizes that he is guilty of deliberately forming false ideas about China: "He had allowed him [Peter] to grow up with a sentimental notion of what China was like. He had even helped to make the notion... But he had wanted the children to understand the glory of China, the honor, the dignity of an ancient race and country. He purposely dwelled upon these things. It was necessary to do this to have a perspective upon the disagreeable present."

The novel "Relatives" touches on the issue of reality and fakeness "ours" and "someone else's". Recognizing the characters' hybridity as a new reality and norm is more important than creating "pseudo-authenticity" and excessively actualizing one's national essence. Pearl Buck's characters can't give up one of the components of their self, Chinese or American, they must be reconciled. "Understanding hybridity requires a shift from an either/or understanding to a both/and understanding," the authors of The Cambridge History of American Literature emphasize.

The main theme of the novel "Relatives" is the theme of self-identification, traditional for modern multicultural literature in the United States. The heroes of the novel combine communal and individual consciousness and experience an urgent desire to comprehend all layers of their fragmented identity.

Conclusion. The problem of cultural identity in the novels of Pearl Buck occupies a leading place in the works of many Chinese researchers. In the article by Guo Ying-zen and Hao Sun-ling "The Pearl Buck Phenomenon" (1997), researchers focus on the hybrid identity of Pearl Buck herself, her balancing on the edge of two cultures, which is reflected in her work. Researchers even call Buck the founder of ideas about a "world without borders."

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